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- 20190517_OO_student6_Transcript0...
- 20190517_OO_student7_CODE.txt
- 20190517_OO_student7_Transcript0...
- 20190517_OO_student8_CODE.txt
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- 20190521_OO_student9_CODE.txt
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- 20190523_OO_student11_CODE.txt
- 20190523_OO_student11_Transcript...
- 20190523_OO_student12_CODE.txt
- 20190523_OO_student12_Transcript...
- 20190604_OO_student14_CODE.txt
- 20190604_OO_student14_tran...
- main.tex

File outline

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1 [00:00:00]
2
3 R: OK, so I have a little task of code reading and I'd like to ask you, this is the question that I wanna ask you.
4 S: OK: Describe the purpose of this code. In other words if the code would be placed in a function, give an appropriate
   name for the function. Alright so, you have an integer array which consists of 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8. (Hopefully I did
   myself) 8 elements and we have an integer which is equal to 25, then for the integer value in the array if the value is
   bigger, smaller than the current, then the current becomes the value. And then you system out, print, the current one. So
   technically you just go through the entire array, you compare the first element which was initialised with the integer
   current and you compare integer current to, well, the entire array, to all elements in the array and well the one that is
   the biggest, technically, will be printed out at the end. Yes.
5 R: OK, so what would you call the function?
6 S: Well, ok like "search for the highest element".
7 R: Yeah ok.
8 S: Or like, "search highest" [Silence for 5 seconds] of a list
9
10 [00:01:27]
11
12 R: OK great. Now I'm going to ask you a few questions and these questions I'm going to ask them to you every time. I wanna
   ask you about the code that you looked at.
13 [R reconfigures screens]
14
15 [00:01:50]
16
17 R: There, now you see the code. One thing is the program code that you have, so the algorithm. How difficult did you find
   the algorithm?
18 S: Ehh...
19 R: And the other question is, let me, I'll explain the questions first, the other one is: How difficult did you find the
   concepts and definitions? And concepts are like, there's an array, there's an... You know?
20 S: Yeah.
21 R: So if you look at the program code, how complex do you perceive it?
22
23 [00:02:13]
24
25 S: Seeing first is the first question. I wouldn't say it's much like, OK let's not code zero or one. Because zero or one
   would be like, integer plus integer, system out that thing. That would be zero or one. So for a person who is a complete
   beginner...
26 R: Yeah
27 S: Looking at the array he must first know the indexes of the array and that begins with like zero is the first element to
   the number of elements minus one. Eh... So now he must know that this integer becomes this value, so... That is easy for
   now and then the for-loop is the enhanced for-loop, which is studied in the third quarter at least in the study program
   here. So if you don't know how this works this could be a bit hard, but eh... I mean I know how it works, so I wouldn't say
   it's hard. And then you have a simple if-statement you just check for the condition, whether this is true or not. And if it
   is you do the code inside and if it is not then you proceed to the other element, because of the for-loop. And once the for-
   loop is finished you system out, so you print out.
28
29 [00:03:28]
30
31 R: Because the for-loop you say how it works, you can't see from what it says there what it does.
32 S: No, not this one. If you use the normal one for the normal integer: i is zero, i stops at that value, increment i,
   because then you get the idea that, that you code the name of the array and you put the index there. So kinda like, you can
   see which element you're talking about. But right now you're just calling value and value is just any value from the array,
   which has to be called and you know like you don't... Eh... It's a bit weird like, I know what it is, but at the beginning
   it was hard to see that this is an array. If it wasn't for Netbeans to correct it, I wouldn't use this one. At all. I would
   just stick with the normal one. Even though it's like more typing.
33
34 [00:04:12]
35
36 R: Because it's more?
37 S: Because it is more clear to me what it does. Because take a look at array at index 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 which is incremented
   by the for-loop.
38 R: would you say that this is almost magic?
39 S: No, I'd go with like 3 or 4, like the farthest one from this thing here. It's pretty self explanatory. So if I go this,
   I'll go with 3.
40 R: OK, go ahead.
41 S: OK.
42
43 [00:04:40]
44
45 R: But I mean the enhanced for-loop itself, is that like magic? Because it doesn't, you have to know, memorise, what it...
46 S: Yeah, yeah, you have to know like the distance the integer value in the array, in the rain values. So that's like this
   thing here it looks almost like functional programming.
47 [laughing]
48 S: I've never seen it, but, like I don't see it clearly like the increment there and stuff, so.
49
50 [00:05:08]
51
52
53 S: OK, so now the second one: The task covered concepts and definitions that I perceived as very complex. Eh... I don't
   think so. Ah, like it's just a simple if-statement, so I'd go with like zero or one.
54 R: Yeah and the index right? You said you have to understand what an index is. And that it starts at zero, but...
55 S: Well yeah that's pretty much what you get at like lecture 4 (of Object Orientation? quotation needed), or so it's kinda
   like easy-ish. So I'm gonna go with like 0 or 1, let's go with 1.
56
57 [00:05:35]
58
59 S: Then the instructions and explanations during the task were very unclear. Well there we're no... Oh you mean the
   instructions here?
60 R: Yeah.
61 S: Well, I mean, ah it was clear so I'd go with...
62 R: Well a low number means clear.
63 S: Ok, and this.
64
65 [00:05:54]
66
67 R: Alright thank you. Now I have another question that looks...
68 S: This is the output, or not?
69 R: Yeah no but we are not gonna run it. I'm gonna, I know that you can run the code but I'm gonna ask you not to. OK.
70
71 [00:06:05]
72
73 S: Is not discredibile for this code. In other words either code would be placed in a function. Give an appropriate name for

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Track changes is off

You: S2: FOR understandable
Jan 6, 2024 2:58 PM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S1: construct familiarity important
Jan 6, 2024 4:49 PM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S2: FOR understandable - clear
how it works
Jan 7, 2024 8:02 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S3: FOREACH not traceable/clear
how it works
Jan 7, 2024 8:04 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

the function. So the same thing. Eh... Again we have an array which has 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 again 8 elements and now you're declaring another, the same integer, current, which is being initialised as the first element of the array, in this case 25. Then you have another integer i which is set to 0. And then while 0 is smaller than the length of the array, which is an extra function, but it's like in the find in like any IDE when you click dot you can see it. It's like pretty self explanatory, what it means like this means going through the array so while technically 0 is smaller than 8 if the... eh...if... The array at the zeroth position is bigger than the current position then the current becomes the zeroth position. And then you increment i. Then you system out. And then cut it.

74
75 [00:07:14]
76
77 S: OK so this one is a bit more dubious. The thing is you don't technically this statement never holds because i is zero and i doesn't change so you're basically just comparing if eh... the array at zero is bigger than the same value, which is never the case. So this never gets, the if-statement never triggers. And you're just like checking this 8 times. And then you print out 25.
78 R: So what should we call it?
79 S: Eh... I don't know. "Useless check"?
80 R: Ok, good. [types]
81
82 [00:07:55]
83
84 R: Ok, and if you look at the code that there is, how difficult do you find the code?
85 S: Eh... This one was a bit more tricky, because you don't really have. Oh no wait, wait, wait, wait. Ok [laughs] I now see that you're incrementing i. Then i becomes. Oh wait then i becomes 1 and then 1 is 70. So then you go 70 bigger than 25. It is. Ok so this is like the same thing traversing the array, but with a while-loop. Ok. So forget what I said about the earlier statement. Yeah.
86 R: No problem, you can change it, you can change it.
87
88 [00:08:33]
89
90 R: So what did you not see that you see now?
91 S: Eh... Like I looked here, like on this bar, from the while until the end of the while and I saw that i does not change there and I thought that we would just like keep on looping i and that i would stay initialised as 0. But i changes by incrementing it by 1.
92 R: But you read this line to me. But did you think it was outside the brackets then? Or did you just forget it?
93
94 [00:09:00]
95
96 S: I just forgot it. No, no actually. I didn't forget it. I, like I imagined that it would stop the loop and I knew it and I didn't like think that like i would change like this way. It's kinda like a for-loop. I mean it kinda like it is. Like you're just incrementing i and then i becomes like 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7. So then...
97 R: So you say it works just like a for-loop?
98 S: Yeah. So this one was a bit more, like...
99 R: Well that doesn't matter. Yeah.
100
101 [00:09:28]
102
103 S: Yeah this one [clicks]. Ok, so it is not a "useless check".
104 R: No you can go ahead, it doesn't matter. It's good.
105 S: Let us call it "complex search" or "complex highest" I guess. Because your getting the highest element as possible, but you get it in a much more complex way.
106 R: You say that because of the while-loop?
107 S: Yes. **Usually while-loop for 00-beginners won't be used to traverse an array.** At all. Because, like bad things happen. I mean if it's like a one dimensional array you could do it, but still a for-loop is like much more like common. So given the fact that it actually tricked me, I would go with like 5 or 6 here. Let's go for 6.
108
109 [00:10:14]
110
111 S: Now eh... The task was again clear.
112 R: Now hold on, first the concepts and definitions.
113 S: Yeah yeah I mean like the concepts and definitions are still clear. You had to check the highest element, but I just thought that you never go to any higher element. So the task is still clear. It's just the thing up here that kept me confused.
114 S: Eh... The instructions were again very clear. Like you just have to name the function. So not really that hard.
115 R: Ok, ok now good.
116
117 [00:10:49]
118
119 R: I have one more code reading question.
120 S: Alright so eh... First you have an array, again with 8 elements, I think. Yes 8. Then you have an integer which produces 0. You call it count. Then for, like the normal for-loop now, or like the less enhanced for-loop. The integer i which is declared as a zero, i smaller than the length of the array, in this case 8, and then you increment i. Then you want to check if the array value, so the array at the position of y or technically at index 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 is equal to 0. And if it is, increase a counter and then the system will out print the count.
121
122 [00:11:41]
123
124 S: Now there is only one case where the value of the array will be 0. It's at value 6. You're still gonna traverse it there. So the value of count is 1 at the end. So this one was actually easier than the last one. This was really straightforward.
125 R: And what would you say the purpose is of the code?
126 S: Ehm... Whah, just like check for how many zeroes you have and you just count them, I guess. So "zero counter".
127
128 [00:12:20]
129
130 R: And you say this one is easier. What makes this one easier than the other ones?
131 S: Yeah, ehmm this one was like, more like intuitively made, because this is the type of thing that you would see how arrays would be used. For-loop and then inside the if-statements or switch cases to check on conditions. So this one was like pretty straightforward. All you have to do is like keep track of elements that are 0 if there are any elements that go to zero increment the counter. A possible mistake in this case could happen if you would assume that you always increment the counter, or like if you fail the first time then you don't proceed for the rest of the array. But eh.. I mean after, maybe like one hour of practice would know this, so it's not really that big of a problem.
132 R: But you also said that this is the way you would normally approach it.
133 S: Yes.
134
135 [00:13:17]
136
137 R: That means that you also have to know about the standard approaches.
138 S: Yes.
139 R: So you have to know those as well. Because we are talking about things you have to learn, so you have to know about syntax but you also have to know about standard plans. So...
140 S: Yes, well you know in this case eh... at least in this university there are like code examples in the slides and like you begin doing things with arrays since lecture 4 and you do this until the fourth quarter and you keep on doing this, because...
141
142 [00:13:42]
...

You: O6; considers construct-plan combination
Jan 7, 2024 8:10 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

143
144 R: In IP or 00?
145 S: Yes in IP, definitely in IP [laughter]. Ehm... So how did I say it like, the whole thing about programming is more like, at least the way I see it, stack and trees, the quad trees and binary trees. And these trees can proceed values. And there are two types of values like, primitive values and like array values which are like arrays just like a lot of primitive values. And yeah so you're gonna use arrays all the time and after like the fourth or fifth lecture you probably know how to do this and it's no longer a problem. So I would rate the code with like a 2, it wasn't so hard, it wasn't complex.

146
147 [00:14:29]
148
149 S: The concepts and definitions. Ehm... No they weren't. In fact they were even easier than last time.
150 R: And what made it easier?
151 S: Well, [laughter] the fact that I have practiced.
152 R: Yeah, yeah you've practiced the for-loop. So you've practiced the for-loop more often than the while?
153 S: Yes, yeah that's true, but also the while-loop is made a bit more like. Actually no, it's my fault, I just got confused here because I looked at the i being there at 0. So I stopped. It's my fault. It's actually more complex still. And again it was clear what I had to do, so...

154
155 [00:15:08]
156
157 S: Now for the next one?
158 R: Yeah, hold on. I have here the three pieces of code [takes sheets of paper]. This was the enhanced for-loop. This is the while-loop and this is the normal for-loop. Can you put that in order of most complex to easiest? Which one do you prefer?

159
160 [00:15:23]
161
162 S: Oh well the easiest would definitely be the normal for-loop. Like you use it the most, you are going to use this the most in your coding so like at some point it becomes like really easy to use it for loops. Ehm... I would go with the while-loop next, because even though I messed up on this one, like people are going to study while-loop even before for-loops. That's in the first lecture, you have to do while and if. So it's really easy. It's just that one you have to use while with arrays, which is like unnatural. Or at least I see it as unnatural. Especially if you do like multidimensional arrays, then it's gonna go terribly wrong. So... yeah I'm still gonna place it second, because I don't expect to use while-loops with arrays anyway. And then the enhanced for-loop is like very new syntax, so it took me a while to like get use to it and if the piece of code here was like more complex it would like make it worse than the while-loop.

163 R: Ok, alright but the inside is almost the same right. So we're gonna put them in what order? Ok thank you.
164
165 [00:16:33]
166
167 R: Now we're going to write a little bit of code. I'm gonna ask you not to press the run-button. It's there but don't, it's more about the way you're thinking. This is the question.
168 [00:16:42]
169 [BEGIN TASK 81]
170
171 S: A weather station kept track of rainfall for a number of days. There is an example, so you have an array of rain values, which are 8 indexes long. Like once you get used to the for-loop like you always count the indexes, even if you don't need to. I just do that. In this example you can see that it rained 76 millimetres on the wettest day. This happened on the second day. Write a program that prints on how many days the maximum amount of rain fell.
172 R: So it happened on 2 days.
173 S: It happened on 2 days, yeah yeah OK. Yeah 76. Write a program that prints on how many days the maximum number of...
174
175 [00:17:29]
176
177 S: Ok so... Eh... I will write my code. First of all we need an integer to keep track of the like how many days. So integer let's just say "dayNumber". So be sure to use meaningful names. Let us begin at 0. Now in C++ you might not need to initialise it, but in Java you have to otherwise you get a nullpointer exception. So do this and then you just... Eh... How do I do it? So you have to traverse the array. That's technically doing a for-loop and I can use the normal one. [mumbles] There a [incomprehensible mumble, helper function doesn't get recognised by the IDE]

178
179 [00:18:18]
180
181 R: That's not that important, I see that you're using it. So it's good.
182 S: OK. Then I have to, oh it's actually a good idea to actually make another integer. Say eh... integer "highest" or "wettest". I just name it to what was the highest value and I'll compare if eh... Rain values at position i equal this value, equal wettest. And if this is the case then eh... Then dayNumber++. And then you can print out this number, although you don't have to. But like, System.out eh... It's not out of memory. [Silently typing for 5 seconds] Then you just have to print the value.
183 S: Yeah.
184 [00:19:20]
185 [END TASK 81]
186
187 [DISCUSS TASK 81]
188 R: Yeah.
189 S: Yeah, I usually write it faster, so that's not really a problem, I'm just not used to Chromebooks.
190 R: Yeah, the keyboard. Ok, thank you very much. Let's see...
191
192 [00:19:30]
193
194 S: There are also many other ways to do it.
195 R: Yeah?
196 S: Like, what you could do, another way is just, instead of like declaring this number you just like check how many times it triggers. So we do a while-loop and check how many times would you get this value again and then you'd... well use a counter again. Ok, so you use a counter, technically.

197
198 [00:19:57]
199
200 R: And what's the advantage of doing that?
201 S: Of doing the while-loop over the for-loop? Ehm... There is no advantage to this and technically they both need to traverse the array. What happens is the while-loop is going to increment your value i, which I have to also declare somewhere else. And it's gonna go 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and then 6, 7. Until it got through the entire array. The same thing happens in the for-loop. The for-loop checks, it begins at 0 and it checks 'is zero bigger than the length of the array'. If it is not, increment i with 1. And since i gets incremented and your eh... you've got like you're testing if the rain value at i is equal to wettest. Then... hhm... i being incremented then you're gonna go through the entire array.

202 R: Alright, OK.
203
204 [00:20:55]
205
206 R: I have the same questions for you. The code, how difficult did you find it?
207 S: Uhhh... I'll go with 3. Or 2, let's go with 2. Uhhh... Now the task covered concepts and definitions that I perceived as very complex. Hmm... I don't think so. Like this was technically checking ehmm... a bar from the sketch about the rain days. This was technically about sketching, ehmm... like trying to find out like how many times you have the largest element in your array. which will be needed for sorting later. So I would say maybe 1?
208 R: Ok.
209
210 [00:21:37]
211
212 S: Then the instructions well it was pretty I would still go with 1 like if it was like find the largest element of

You: S1: construct familiarity, most practiced
Jan 7, 2024 8:13 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve

Reply

213
214 [00:22:10]
215
216 R: Ok, if I give you this. Where would you be able to...
217 S: Write a program on how many days the max amount of rain fell.
218 R: Yes, that is the one we just did. Where would you put that in your...
219 S: Well I wouldn't say that reading code is easier than writing code. Although writing code is still, like, a bit harder. Like a friend of mine he can write almost everything. He, it takes him like a few hours and he can still come up with it. But if you ask him to explain what he did he just says "it works, I don't know".
220 R: Ok, but now I'm going to ask you not about, because now I asked you to write and then I asked you to read, but if you look at the complexity of the code. So you see this code is that more difficult than what you see lying there?
221
222 [00:23:00]
223
224 S: Hmm... No, I don't think so. It's like really close to the first one, with the normal for-loop.
225 R: Because?
226 S: Oh, well because... Eh... You do the same thing but in this you search for 0 while here you make another integer that you have to search for. So I would still maybe like place it here.
227 R: Okay.
228 S: Or maybe like here. Part from the intense was mostly there.
229 R: Okay great.
230 S: I mean I still didn't use enhanced for-loop, so there's that.
231 R: Yeah, alright ok.
232 [END DISCUSS TASK 81]
233
234 [00:23:40]
235
236 [BEGIN TASK 83B]
237 S: First and last rainy days. So eh... a weather station kept track of rainfall for a number of days. Here is an example and there you get the array again. Write a program that prints the index of the first rainy day and the index of the last rainy day. If there are no rainy days, print an error message. Ooooh. Ok so I kinda see like it's a big like blur now, because now it says a program that prints the index. So not like the value of the index but the index itself. So I have to print 0 and the last one. So I can just like say... Eh... At least the way that I see it here
238
239 [00:24:25]
240
241 S: I can just says system or just like declare integer eh... first be 0 and then you just say another integer which will be 7. From a completely like unintuitive way, like, a complete beginner just by reading the text here I get the impression that I have to put in the indexes. So index 0 and index 7, not the values, so if I, I mean I understand I have to put in 25 and 34, but they way I read it here but if I didn't know how to do it would just be like system.printout, print line sorry, and it was just like print eh... first, some space, and last. [talks during typing] That's pretty much the way I get it.
242
243 [00:25:19]
244
245 R: Ok and what if there are no rainy days? Print an error message?
246 S: Check if there are any rainy days. You must now, eh... go in a for-loop and [types while talking] I can do an integer i is 0. I mean the integer doesn't matter. i is smaller than... Then i++ and eh... I have to check. So, what does like rainy day mean? A day with rain? So is 0 counted as rainy day? I have to check.
247 R: No, 0 is a dry day and 1 is a rainy day and 2 is rainy day and 3 is a rainy day, ...
248
249 [00:26:10]
250
251 S: I don't have to check if the array is empty, I have to check if the rain is at 0. Ok, so ehmm... I could make another element, another integer which would be more intuitive. But since I already have an integer which is at 0 I'm gonna check if rainy at i equals first. Eh... No. If there are no rainy days, eh... we have to check if all of them are not equal to the first one, then eh... system.printout eh... yeah. [Silent typing] Let's just print this error.
252
253 [00:27:19]
254
255 S: Let's see if I did it correctly, so if the thing is not equal to first print error. No that's a bit wrong. Because then I would get a case where this is not equal. So even if I do it at equal then I get at a point where there is 0, so in this case I would do print the error message. Uhm... which is wrong. Ok, let me see how did I do that.
[silence for 10 seconds]
256
257 [00:28:13]
258
259 S: I wonder how you place the if-statement. Ehm... [silence for 8 seconds]
260
261 [00:28:28]
262
263 S: This is actually pretty hard. Wait. Ehm... You have to check if... [silence for 6 seconds]
264
265 [00:28:42]
266
267 S: Yeah so like I have to do a return, oh but this is a main so I can't return anything. Eh... Well, I need to break the program then. Because the check if there is at least one, the first one is and then if it is not... [silence for 7 seconds]
268
269 [00:29:19]
270
271 S: No it is nothing. Well [laughter]. Because you have 0. [silence for 35 seconds] [slow typing for 8 seconds]
272
273 [00:30:08]
274
275 S: I got, let's see. Eh... [silence and slow typing for 25 seconds]
276
277 [00:30:37]
278
279 R: What are you doing now?
280 S: Well right now I'm checking if... I'm not sure if I'll get an error. Like a compile error at this point. I'm checking if the current eh... Like current day if the current day is equal to 0 and if the day before it is equal to 0. Which I'm pretty sure that I get an error, because on the first one I must go to the one before, so I think that I should just like use a NOR.
281
282 [00:31:13]
283
284 S: Oh that's wrong. So we're just gonna go -1. Instead we also check not today and the previous day, but today and the next day and this way will not go out of bound. And eh... and this thing here should be this thing. And now if they're both at 0 so it's gonna go first then second element, third fourth, eh... fifth, sixth, seventh eight, now this, at least in this case works. But if I get like all zeroes but one that rains, this is no longer going to work. So technically I kinda need to hard code this in this scenario. Or I need to like an extra... I don't know...
285
286 [END TASK 83B (PREMATURELY)]
287

You: O7: patchwork process. First design doesn't work, gets stuck trying to fix it
Jan 7, 2024 8:30 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O1: misconception. Using "(rainValues[i]==first && rainValues[i+1]==first)" and thinks this will not go out of bound
Jan 7, 2024 8:27 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

288 [00:32:05]
289 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 83B]
290
291 R: Given what you managed we'll just leave it like this and I'm going to ask you, now that you have a feeling about the code, how, how?
292 S: I would think it is fine. First of all, it was a bit unclear what was meant by 'print indexes', so...
293 R: So that for the bottom one, the instructions are not...
294
295 [00:32:31]
296
297 S: Now, how hard it is, everything was fine. The syntax is easy, until you get to the if-statement. Things that you have to consider: many cases and **it's really hard to exclude all cases with one if-statement**. Now, what I could do is: I could make many if-statements or I could nest if-statements, but I tried to use only one. Because with nested I can just like check if any of those hold or just like do else if else if else if. But if I am to use only one if-statement it, although there was not specified not to use only one, I would... It will get a bit harder. **It has to be hard coded, at least in this case.**
298
299 [00:33:13]
300
301 S: Hmm... I get that if you are like a beginner and you don't really know else if and like nesting these statements you like try to solve these programs and you give him this one first then he expects like an **if-statement inside a loop then getting out of this if-statement is, at least for me, I think impossible**. To get it like completely done for the general, for all cases. It is really hard to expect all elements of the array and like check if not even one is equal to 0. To check if all of them are not equal to zero. Because like, computers can like check one at the time and then if I had done like ehm... like without this part it will always be...
302 R: Without what's behind the 'and' you mean?
303
304 [00:34:03]
305
306 S: Yes. Then it would eventually get to a point where it goes, this is 0. It's gonna print ehm.. well there is an error.
307 R: Ok, but you did choose to use one if-statement and an 'and'.
308 S: Yes.
309 R: Could you've also done it, why did you choose that instead of...
310 S: Nesting?
311 R: Yeah.
312
313 [00:34:23]
314
315 S: Or like using many? Then I could probably, like, do it for all cases, but ehm... At least I thought that I had to like make it as simple as possible. Like, imagine if you're a complete beginner and you don't really know that you can nest these statements that one case will follow only after the other one, then I just decided to do this.
316 R: So does that mean that you find nesting more difficult?
317
318 [00:34:53]
319
320 S: Ehm... It's not necessarily more difficult, It's like hmm... you have to know this would trigger only after the first triggers. So you shouldn't really ehm... **If you nest you have to be careful for the most, for the parent, like the most out, like the most out, like the one that goes first.**
321 R: Above it yeah.
322 S: The one that's the most above.
323 R: It's more the flow that you have to keep track of.
324
325 [00:35:22]
326
327 S: **Because if you have to do many statement and like you exclude conditions and then your final thing is sold by an if-statement again, then it's really hard that you're gonna make it there. Well bad news because somewhere in the beginning something it was never done. Although it's hard coded so I have to like mention this. And hard coded means that it's not gonna work for all cases. It's gonna work for this case specifically, but again if I had like 0 0 here it would print "error". If I had any two zeroes together then it would print "other one". So technically you could keep on going with "and's like forever, which is a bad idea. [silence for 3 seconds]**
328
329 [00:36:13]
330
331 S: So I would rate this at 5 or 6. If you know how to do nesting, then you're probably go for 5. But if you don't then 6. Because I didn't use nested things and now that you use like else if's then I'd go with a 6. Now the task covered concepts and definitions that I perceived as very complex. Ehm... what does that that mean like concepts and definitions?
332 R: Concepts: you have an array, you're indexing, you're using a for-loop. You're using the double 'and'.
333
334 [00:36:47]
335
336 S: If-statement? Oh the double 'and'. **Ok so the double 'and' can be tricky, because for this to print both statements, both booleans must be true**. Because asking if ehm... i is equal to 0 or i-1 is equal to 0 can have either the meaning of True or False. So they both must have a value of True. To proceed I would say it's gonna be like 3 or 4. I'm gonna go with 4.
337
338 [00:37:15]
339
340 S: And the instructions and/or explanations during the tasks were very clear. Ehm... Ok so this one was indeed unclear because, as again, stated print the indexes and print again the index would at least for me mean print 0 and print 7. Like don't print their values. Like the program been like print the rains trend or something, like how wet was it that day. That would mean like print these values. But the index clearly states 0 7.
341
342 [00:37:57]
343
344 R: Alright. This is the question you just did. How would you, how complex did you find it?
345 S: Well, the needed for the correct if and well the unclear statement, the unclear stating of the question was it the hardest of them all.
346 R: And if you look at the complexity of how difficult the code is? Because you're now saying that the question was not clear.
347
348 [00:38:23]
349
350 S: Hmm... I guess the code wasn't so hard. You're just trying to get the correct if which can be done or might not be done. I don't know like, it was ok for me.
351 R: OK, alright.
352 S: Let's go the next one?
353 R: Yeah click on that one.
354 [END DISCUSS TASK 83B]
355 [00:38:45]
356
357 [BEGIN TASK 90]
358 S: So the next one is: a weather station kept track of rainfall for a number of days, here is an example. The standard array uses 5 elements. 3, 4, 0, 1, 2. We want to plot this in a horizontal bar chart. Each row should show the daily rainfall using asterisks.
359 R: Asterisks, those are the stars.
360 S: Oh yeah ok. One asterisk for each millimetre of rain. In this example the following would be printed. So if you get, depending on the values you have to print the number of, these number of stars. Write a program that prints a horizontal

Resolve Reply

You: O2: considers hardcoding
Jan 7, 2024 8:28 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

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You: S7: logical operators difficult
Jan 7, 2024 9:27 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: O2: considers hardcoding
Jan 7, 2024 8:31 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O3: lacking terminate plan (plan to break out of a loop)
Jan 7, 2024 8:33 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S17: nesting increases difficulty
Jan 7, 2024 8:35 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S16: multiple conditional statements difficult to keep track of
Jan 7, 2024 8:32 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S7: logical operators difficult (refers to && with double 'and')
Jan 7, 2024 8:37 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

361 bar chart using the stars to show the daily rainfall.

362 [00:39:30]

363

364 S: Ok so first you must get all the elements of the array. You can do it in a dumb way and you can just like use ehm... like hard coding or you can do a for-loop, which is the ideal one, the ideal way here. Or like anywhere. [typing silently for 18 seconds]

365

366 [00:40:06]

367

368 S: Now you should nest another loop here. So I'll go and declare an integer to count the number of stars. And then you do while then another integer. Oh no I don't think, actually now we go for the rain values at 1. Eh... [silent typing for 5 seconds]

369

370 [00:40:42]

371

372 So as long as count is like smaller than the rain, than the rain value or 3, 4, 0, 1, 2, you will be printing aaah... system... Then you'll be printing well a star. Either a character or a string value. And I must be careful what print to use, because if you use printline it will print them on the new line. And now you want to use printline here. [silently typing for 5 seconds] with basically nothing, so that you can get a newline and that should be it.

373

374 [00:41:37]

375

376 R: Ok.

377 S: So, let's, let's check again. You're starting from the first value and then you begin so this is now 3, this is now 0. While 3 is bigger than 0, wait I forgot to increment the counter. Ehm... Yes now it's fine, because otherwise it'd be like an endless loop. Ehm... yeah so now the counter, the counter is 0, 1, 2, 3. [silence for 4 seconds, continuing mumbling]

378

379 [00:42:17]

380

381 S: Hmm... Then it is 0, 1, 2, then we go again. Hmm...

382

383 [00:42:33]

384

385 R: What are you thinking about?

386 S: I'm thinking about if it's gonna go like one more loop, that's not needed, because eh... It's just about the while-condition, so count begins at 0 and the rain values will be 3, 4, 0, 1 or 2. So take for example 3, you're gonna check is 0 bigger than, smaller than 3? Yes it is: print. Is 1 smaller than, so then we have one print, then we need to go for 1. Is 17 yes it is. Is 2? Yes it is. Is 3? No it's not. Oh, so it's fine. So this is the correct one. Just had to like think about it for a second. Eh... yeah that's pretty much it.

387 [00:43:15]

388 [END TASK 90]

389 R: Ok, ok then this was the last question where you needed to program code.

390 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 90]

391 [00:43:23]

392

393 R: How complex did you find this? If you look at this code.

394 S: Now this was the nesting array you was talking about. There was like another way that you can proceed those without nesting. Ehm... The thing is, I have to do two loops, one inside each other. Ehm... This is a bit tricky, especially if it's not like two for-loops. When it's two for-loops you mainly use it for multidimensional arrays, which is like, again really intuitive once you get used to it. But like a while-condition and a for-loop outside of it will trigger as following. So the while-loop will trigger once, then the whole while-loop will continue until it stops. Then the for-loop will increment to do it again and the while-loop will trigger ehm... like completely again. Then the for-loop will go again and so on. And you have to know how to stop the while-loop, because I just forgot to do the counter, it will go forever.

395

396 [00:44:20]

397

398 S: Ehm... Also about the printing. In C++ it's really a bit easier, cause there the printing is just on a single line and if you want to end a line you have to do an endl and here you have to keep, like, track of what you're printing.

399 R: You mean the difference between the print and the printline?

400

401 [00:44:39]

402

403 S: Yeah, printline, because printline, if you do printline on the place of the print you're gonna print any vertical, any horizontal bars, you're gonna print them vertically. So that's, like, not ideal. And well that's about it. I guess maybe, maybe like nesting things can be like nasty, because like, with a while-loop it's not only the thing that is looping, so ehm... So for the for-loop it's like really clear like when it stops, but now booleans in the while-loop can be tricky, like when does it stop? If you think about it in the beginning of IP there was this case where we played with the Charles in Charles world.

404 R: Oh Karel, ja ja ja.

405 S: Yeah Karel, XXX.

406 R: Oh Charles in English yeah.

407

408 [00:45:30]

409

410 S: So you had, you had booleans and not like integer values being incremented. And these booleans would be 'while not in front of a wall', 'while on a ball', 'while not on a ball' and then you had to like keep track of when those would end. Like when they would terminate. Like just walk into a wall and kill yourself. So I guess that was a bit more complex I'd go with like 6, 7? Maybe 8. Because, like, the while-loop is like, each statement must have a boolean condition and this boolean condition will continue on forever if you mess it up.

411

412 [00:46:07]

413

414 S: Now the task covered concepts and definitions that I perceived as very complex. Eh... now the nesting is a bit hard, is a bit more nasty. And yeah I guess that's pretty much it. I'll go with 5.

415 R: And you say if it would be a for in a for is that harder then the while in a for?

416

417 [00:46:25]

418

419 S: Well continuing that I didn't use a for in a for. Well the problem is that it is not in this particular case, but ehm... You could use this whole thinking the for-loop in the while-loop here. Like put it in your second condition in the for-loop and then you have to increment the count so technically it would be, this would be replaced with this. But then I think that this, like, I don't see it intuitively before me, it's like I, I've been doing it like this so I don't like to use the for-loop to use like a nested loops unless I'm not like using a multidimensional array.

420 R: And for a multidimensional array you're using a double for-loop?

421

422 [00:47:22]

423

424 S: Eh... Yeah a double for-loop would be much better, because then you have to also keep the counter. Here you have to be careful how you make the counter, while with the double for-loop it's just like intuitive, because the second for-loop indices the columns and the first for-loop indices the rows. If you do it like normally. I OO we got an assignment were they mix those two together and then the first for-loop, so the nested one, the one inside was referencing the row, so you'd go through the array like this. Instead of working on it like this, like normally. So that, that could be a bit more tricky in the beginning and yeah that's pretty much it. Then after you...

425

You: O2: considers hardcoding
Jan 7, 2024 8:40 AM • Edit

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You: O10: minor forget and then recall (and fixes what het forgets)
Jan 7, 2024 8:41 AM • Edit

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You: S21: unconfident flow control - requires lots of explicit thought
Jan 7, 2024 9:30 AM • Edit

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You: S9: nested loops as a plan are easy
Jan 7, 2024 8:43 AM • Edit

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You: S17: nesting increases difficulty
Jan 7, 2024 8:52 AM • Edit

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Resolve Reply

You: S18: nesting conditional more difficult than nested loop
Jan 7, 2024 8:53 AM • Edit

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You: S6: WHILE is error prone
Jan 7, 2024 8:55 AM • Edit

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Resolve Reply

You: S12: tailoring plans difficult. Has plan with nested-FOR in mind for multidimensional arrays, but can't adjust it for this situation, thus goes for the WHILE in the FOR
Jan 7, 2024 9:00 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S9: nested loops easy as plan (for multidimensional arrays)
Jan 7, 2024 8:59 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

426 [00:48:10]
427
428 R: So did you finish the task
429 S: well it wasn't really complex so I'm gonna go with 1. It was like coding this time was a bit harder. That was it.
430 R: And the fact that you'd do this. Where would you put that on your...
431
432 [00:48:25]
433
434 S: Hmm... well it could be just for me, although I would put it as the second hardest, but not the hardest, because I
myself wouldn't like to solve the last one, this one. I would put this like to be harder.
435 R: And what made this one more difficult than the enhanced for?
436 S: The nested for-loops.
437 R: Than the nested for-loops.

Resolve Reply

You: S14: design novel algorithm more difficult than implementing a standard plan - requires more thought
Jan 7, 2024 9:33 AM • Edit

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